

Iodimetric Determination of Organotrithiocarbonates and A Method for the Determination of Mercaptans

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An iodimetric method for the determination of organotrithiocarbonates in aqueous medium is described. The method has been extended to the determination of mercaptans after their quantitative conversion to trithiocarbonates and iodimetric titrations of the latter. The proposed methods are simple, accurate, reliable and widely applicable.

ORGANOTRITHIOCARBONATES¹ find various applications in industry, medicine, agriculture and analysis, but their determination does not appear to have attracted attention. The present communication reports the iodimetric determination of these compounds, based on the oxidation of —C—S⁻ group to the disulphide.

The method has been extended to the determination of mercaptans after their quantitative conversion to the corresponding trithiocarbonates (through reaction with carbon disulphide and alkali)

and iodimetric titrations of the latter. The proposed methods are simple, accurate, reliable and widely applicable.

Experimental

Reagents

Iodine, 0.05N in water, was prepared by mixing 6.5 g of pure iodine(BDH) and potassium iodide (BDH) in small volume of water until the iodine was completely dissolved, and then diluting the solution to one litre with water. The solution was standardised against pure arsenious oxide solution.

Organotrithiocarbonates: Prepared¹ by shaking an equimolar mixture of corresponding mercaptan, potassium hydroxide and carbon disulphide at a temperature below 10°. The compounds were recrystallised from suitable solvent mixtures and kept in a vacuum desiccator. The purity of the compounds was checked by non-aqueous redox titration².

Mercaptans: Ethyl mercaptan, isopropyl mercaptan, isobutyl mercaptan and *n*-amyl mercaptan, all commercial grade, were distilled before use. *n*-Propyl mercaptan was prepared by the reported method³.

Phenolphthalein, 0.1% (w/v) solution in acetonitrile.

Carbon disulphide, Riedel German, was used as such.

All other reagents used in this investigation were of guaranteed quality.

Procedure :

Determination of organotrithiocarbonates: Aliquots of the solution in water of organotrithiocarbonates were taken in a titration flask and the volume made to about 50ml with water. The solution was mixed with 1g. of NaHCO₃, cooled to room temperature (24°) and titrated against standard (0.05N) iodine solution. The end-point was detected by deep yellow colour imparted to the solution by the first drop of oxidant solution in excess. The end-point may, however, be made more perceptible by using starch as an indicator. From the volume of iodine used corresponding to the end-point in each titration, the amount of each trithiocarbonate was calculated. Results are recorded in Table 1.

TABLE 1.—DETERMINATION OF TRITHIOCARBONATES(TTC) AND MERCAPTANS

Compound	Values are means of 10 determinations	
	Amount found*, mg	Amount found**
<i>Organotrithiocarbonates(potassium salts)</i>		
Ethyl TTC	9.98	40.11
isoPropyl TTC	10.03	30.95
isoButyl TTC	9.97	40.08
<i>n</i> -Amyl TTC	9.96	39.94
<i>Mercaptans :</i>		
Ethyl Mercaptan	8.02	30.09
<i>n</i> -Propyl mercaptan	8.04	29.92
isoPropyl mercaptan	7.96	29.94
isoButyl mercaptan	8.02	30.12
<i>n</i> -Amyl mercaptan	7.96	30.06

*Amount of each trithiocarbonate taken, 10 mg ; Amount of each mercaptan taken, 8 mg.

**Amount of each trithiocarbonate taken, 40 mg ; Amount of each mercaptan taken, 30 mg.

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Determinaion of Mercaptans: Aliquots of the solution in acetonitrile of mercaptans were taken in a titration flask, mixed with 2-3 ml of CS_2 , 2 ml of KOH (approx. 1N) and 10 ml of acetonitrile. The contents were shaken and the flask kept for 5 minutes to ensure completion of the reaction. The resulting yellow coloured solution (indicating formation of trithiocarbonates) was diluted with 30 ml of water and neutralised with acetic acid using phenolphthalein as an indicator. The solution was cooled to room temperature (24°) and titrated with iodine as described above. From the volume of standard iodine used corresponding to the end-point in each titration, the amount of resulting trithiocarbonate and consequently the amount of mercaptan was found out. The results are recorded in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

The results recorded in Table 1 show that ethyl-, isopropyl-, isobutyl- and *n*-amyl trithiocarbonates can be determined by iodimetric titrations. The compounds are quantitatively oxidised to the corresponding bis(alkylmercapto thiocarbonyl) disulphides.

The over-all standard deviation calculated from the pooled data of all the titrations performed with 10 and 40 mg of each compound have been found to be 0.039 and 0.068 respectively.

That mercaptans react with carbon disulphide in the presence of alkali to form organotrithiocarbonates, has been made the basis for the determinations of mercaptans. The resulting trithiocarbonates are titrated iodimetrically. Ethyl-, isopropyl-, *n*-propyl-, isobutyl- and *n*-amyl mercaptans have thus been determined. The over-all standard deviation calculated from the pooled data of all the titrations performed with 8 and 30 mg of each mercaptan have been found to be 0.044 and 0.071 respectively.

References

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